

Interested in making the most of **MOOCs**, serious games and online learning communities in your teaching?

Interested in getting inspired on how to use them effectively in a blended learning setting?

Read Anna's story to be introduced to the **INSYSTED** approach!

BEFORE THE INSYSTED APPROACH

"I am a university teacher in the study programme in Industrial Engineering and Management and I am reflecting on how to make the most of my courses.

I would like the students to **engage in the classes more actively and gain practice in digital tools**, in addition to just listening and taking notes."

This booklet is an **inspirational guide** for **university teachers** but also for the **non-academic staff** supporting them in the (re)design of lessons and courses in a **blended learning setting**.

The INSYSTED project (INtegrated SYSTem for European Digital learning) devised an instructional booklet with **practical advice** on how to **foster soft and digital skills and internationalisation** in higher education by using **MOOCs, serious games** and **online learning communities**.

This publication is targeted towards **industrial and management engineering education** but it is meant to be **transferable to any other university context**.

AFTER THE INSYSTED APPROACH

"I decided to use a **small steps approach** and to focus on one critical topic within my course, blending face-to-face and online activities."

If Anna's story intrigued you, you can download the booklet here:

<http://www.alliance4tech.eu/insysted-pedagogical-framework-instructional-booklet/>

INSYSTED involves Alliance4Tech universities: Technische Universität Berlin (coordinator), CentraleSupélec Paris, Politecnico di Milano and UCL University College London.

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